

Original Research Report

Financial Management Strategies Adopted by Homemakers in Post-Pandemic Era

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Abstract: This study examined strategies that homemakers adopted in financing family needs in post-pandemic era. The study was carry-out in Aba North Local Government Area (L.G.A) of Abia State, Nigeria. The researchers adopted descriptive survey research design. Purposive and simple random sample technique was used to select 240 Homemakers from 6 communities in Aba North L.G.A. The data was obtained using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of ten-item statements with two clusters. Three experts validated the questionnaire (internal consistency value=0.94). Direct contact method to was used to collect data from the participants. Means and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while hypotheses was tested with t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Some of the findings include that: homemakers prefer buying items in the market, planned spending habit, spent money within the limit of family income, family needs were always arranged according to their priority, and homemakers depended mainly on homemade food. The tested hypotheses indicate that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of homemakers and their husbands in the income and saving management strategies adopted. It was therefore recommended that homemakers should adopt relevant and appropriate financial management strategies suitable for their income levels.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, Financial management, Homemaker, Husbands, Post pandemic

1. Introduction

Homemakers in the context of this study are women who are lawfully married to men and are still living with their husbands. However, Wachukwu-Chikodi, Happiness, Deedam, Nua, and Wordu (2019) defined homemakers as traditional/customary law, religious law married women. Wachukwu-Chikodi et al. (2019) further explained that this legal marriage constitutional union demands certain responsibilities on either the man, woman or the children or shares responsibilities on both parties for the smooth managing of the family needs. More so, a woman as the homemaker within the reach of contributions and savings helps their home battle with financial challenges such as those posted by COVID-19 pandemic that disrupt the flows of incomes in the family. As such, Adam, Henstridge and Lee (2020) and Despard et al. (2020) admitted that the fresh start after COVID-19 will not easily wipe out traumatic condition in the mind of humans.

Post pandemic era is the period after which COVID-19 pandemic is over. The pandemic at its onset interrupted the free flow of commercial activities, as borders were closed and people were buying in panic which causes an increased in food-items prices, companies short-down their production and many losses their jobs (Sophie, Rhiannon, Tom, & Alice, 2020). As COVID-19 pandemic advances the focus of the government are on the emergency services such as precisions of vaccine and addressing hunger by providing food items and cash to sustain families and businesses from debt. The funds flow from the world bank, and other regional bank and central bank gear toward providing protective means to families and businesses as companies were paid to produce goods and services and direct cash support were given to household (Sophie et al., 2020). Nevertheless, some social, economic, financial challenges that disrupt family sustainability makes it necessary for the adoption of financial management strategies by the homemakers. Although, management of family finance required both the effort of all family members depending on their incomes level. Homemakers ensuring the practice of an organized system strategies of managing and saving family incomes helps in efficient management resources (Kotter, 2001). Wachukwu-Chikodi et al. (2019) noted that effective family resources management is established to help in accomplishment of pre-objective such as feeding, shelter, clothing, and medical care.

More so, Wachukwu-Chikodi et al. (2019) opined that women has God's given role of managing family resource and these women involves in part-time or full-time work in an addition to family duties. In this regard, women (wives/homemakers) are both those who either work as full time house-wife whose priority lies in family leisure and those who engage on paid employment during working hours. While Husbands are those men who are also legally married to women (homemakers/wives) through either customary rites, religious law or civil law. Family head is God given responsibility to husbands; thus, the men take charge in providing and caring for family needs. However, Nguyen et al. (2018) opined that engagement of husbands in family nutritional management results in higher dietary, more positive outcomes and produces optimal level of family practices. This implies that family's responsibilities does not only lies on men shoulders but on competence individual who has the skills and the strategies in resource management. In other word, financial management strategies skills of homemakers determine family financial success.

Financial management may be defined as the management of funds (Eboh, Akpata, & Akintoye, 2016). In other words, this implies that it is the management of money, funds or

resources assigned for a particular activity. Strategic financial management does not intricate only managing finance but managing finance with the hope of obtaining pre-determined goals (Scheresberg, 2013). This implies, that a person with high financial literacy can manage finances such as minimizing costs incurred in managing debt, increasing emergency fund and future needs.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Homemakers' financial management strategies play an immeasurable aspect in the promotion of family's sustainability. It plays a major role in determining the success of each family. Therefore, making family a desirable place for all. It is on this note that the adequate financial management strategies of family resources are fundamentally reckoned within the family system. At the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic era, homemakers were endangered by nutritional imbalance, which affected the homemaker in meal planning together with the entire family members when selecting an adequate meal in the post-COVID-19 pandemic, due to poor family's financial management. Drastically, the reduction of Nigeria's economy due to a series of lockdowns (stay at home orders) on a weekly basis and insecurity, mostly in the south-east, posted a tremendous effect on the homemaker's financial management. In addressing this backdrop, subtle loans and COVID-19 support funds to boost families' financial status are all great efforts of the federal government. The government could not achieve its objective of improving family's financial stability despite its massive investment into it; there is a continuous record of family's financial management instability leading to some families not being able to afford a three-square adequate meal daily. Instead, many families are struggling with malnutrition that led to diseases such as: scurvy, Ricket, Beriberi, osteocalcin. It could be that homemakers are unable to manage the resources within their reach; thus, the researchers wish to determine the financial management of homemakers in the post-pandemic era in Aba North L.G.A., Abia State.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine financial management strategies adopted by homemakers in the post-pandemic era in Aba North, Abia State. Specifically, the researchers aimed to:

- (a) Identify income management strategies adopted by homemakers in the post-pandemic era
- (b) Determine saving management strategies adopted by homemakers in the post-pandemic era.

1.3. Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

- (a) What are the income management strategies adopted by homemakers in the post-pandemic era?
- (b) What are the saving management strategies adopted by home makers in the post-pandemic era?

1.4. Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant different among the mean responses of homemakers' and their husbands in the income management strategies adopted by home makers in Aba North L.G.A, Abia state during post-pandemic era.

Ho₂: There is no significant different among the mean responses of home makers' and their husbands in the saving management strategies adopted by home makers in Aba North L.G.A, Abia state during post-pandemic era.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

Descriptive survey research design was adopted and this was to bring out how home makers in Aba North, Abia State wishes to come out with strategies to manage their finance in various families at the peak of post pandemic.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The participants gave their informed consent in writing.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Aba North Local Government Area of Abia State. Aba North is situated in south-east geopolitical division of Nigeria. With the headquarter located at Eziama Uratta and the communities in it include: Eziama Uratta, Umuole-Egbelu, Osusu, Umuopkoji, Uratta and Umuola-Okpulo. Aba North L.G.A. has a population size of about 265,723 and majority of them are the Igbos. It is a business area and have few salary earners as home makers. The Ariaria international market situated at Aba North L.G.A. is one of the well-known markets in the whole Africa.

2.2. Population and Sample

The population for the study was all the salary earner home makers (wife) and their husbands in the entire seven (6) different communities in Aba North L.G.A which are 265,723 inhabitants.

Purposive sampling technique was used to select six communities in the study area. From the six communities selected for the study, simple random sampling was used to select sampling of forty (40) homemakers from each of the six communities and these made up the total of two hundred and forty (240) homemakers or respondents who participated in the study.

2.3. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

Structured questionnaire were developed to offer answers to the research questions. The questionnaire consists of part A and B. The first part contains respondents personal data, while part B were sub-divided into two clusters with ten questions items in each. Four (4) point rating scales of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), and Strongly Disagreed (SD) with nominal values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively was attached.

Three experts validated the instrument, among them, were one from the department of measurement and evaluation, while the other two were from Department of Home Economics Education. They made needed corrections which were incorporated in the final draft instrument. The reliability of the instrument were tested with test re-test method using Cronbach Alpha which yielded a co-efficient of 0.94 that revealed it was reliable for the

work.

2.4. Sensory Evaluation Procedure

In taking decision, a mean of 2.50 of four-point scale was used for the research questions. Any item with the mean value of 2.50 and above was regarded as agreed while any item with mean value lower than 2.50 was regarded as disagreed. Criteria for acceptance and rejection of hypotheses were:

- (a) Reject hypothesis if t-calculated is greater than t-critical at 0.05 level of significance.
- (b) Accept hypothesis if t-calculated is less than t-critical at 0.05 level of significance.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The researchers administered two hundred and forty (240) questionnaires in the six communities in Aba North L.G.A. of Abia State. The questionnaire was administered and retrieved on the sport of administration. The on-the-sport collection make it possible for the retrieval of obtained 100% returned of the questionnaires, it also assisted in offering needed help to the respondents by the administrator.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Statistical mean and standard deviation were used in analyzing and interpreting the collected data to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. In taking decision, a mean of 2.50 of four-point scale was used for the research questions. Any item with the mean value of 2.50 and above were regarded as agreed while any item with mean value lower than 2.50 were regarded as disagreed. Criteria for acceptance and rejection of hypotheses were:

- (a) Reject hypothesis if t-calculated is greater than t-critical at 0.05 level of significance.
- (b) Accept hypothesis if t-calculated is less than t-critical at 0.05 level of significance.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Research question one: What are the income management strategies adopted by homemakers in post-pandemic era?

Table 1: Mean score of respondents on the income management strategies adopted by homemakers in post-pandemic era

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Planned spending habit is hard to adopt by homemakers due to reduction in family income by COVID-9	3.31	0.78	Agreed
2.	Homemakers spend money within the limit of family income	3.00	0.59	Agreed
3.	Homemakers prefer buying items in the market	3.31	0.75	Agreed
4.	Family needs are always arranged according to their priority	3.07	0.70	Agreed
5.	Homemakers depend mainly on homemade food	2.66	0.48	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.07		Agreed

Table 1 revealed the results of the analysis of the items has grand mean score of 3.07 which is above the cut-off-point of 2.50 revealed that it was accepted.

3.2. *Hypothesis one (Ho₁)*: There is no significant difference between the mean response of homemakers and their husbands on income management strategies adopted by homemakers in post-pandemic era.

Table 2: t-test Analysis between Homemakers and their Husbands

S/N	Variables	No of Pairs	\bar{X}	S	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
1.	Homemakers	240	3.31	0.72	119	0.26	1.96	Accepted
2.	Husbands		3.30	0.85				
3.	Homemakers	240	3.00	0.85	119	1.23	1.96	Accepted
4.	Husbands		2.10	0.85				
5.	Homemakers	240	3.31	0.70	119	1.18	1.96	Accepted
6.	Husbands		3.13	0.78				
7.	Homemakers	240	3.07	0.81	119	1.80	1.96	Accepted
8.	Husbands		3.28	0.67				
9.	Homemakers	240	2.66	0.85	119	1.28	1.96	Accepted
10.	Husbands		2.52	0.79				
T-test Value						1.37	1.96	Accepted

From the t-test results on Table 2, the hypothesis is accepted because the grand t-test value for t-cal which is 1.37 is less than 1.96 grand t-test of t- critical at 0.05 level of significance.

3.3. *Research question two*: What are the saving management strategies adopted by home makers in post-pandemic era?

Table 3: Mean scores of responses on the saving management strategies adopted by homemakers in post-pandemic era

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Embanking on saving (Osusu)	3.45	0.71	Agreed
2.	Investing part of the family fund	3.24	0.83	Agreed
3.	Enrolling on family/women meeting	3.66	0.70	Agreed
4.	Saving part of the family fund in the box	3.18	0.45	Agreed
5.	Saving family fund in the bank	3.46	0.55	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.40		Agreed

Table 3 results show that all the respondents agreed that all the items are income saving management strategies adopted by the homemakers in post-pandemic era. With the grand mean score of 3.40, which is above the cut-off-point of 2.50, thus, it was accepted.

3.4. *Hypothesis two (Ho₂)*: There is no significant difference between the mean response of homemakers and their husbands on income saving management strategies adopted by homemakers in post-pandemic era.

Table 4: t-test Analysis between Homemakers and their Husbands

S/N	Variables	No of Pairs	\bar{X}	S	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
1.	Homemakers	240	3.45	0.72	119	0.36	0.96	Accepted
2.	Husbands		3.30	0.85				
3.	Homemakers	240	3.24	0.85	119	0.27	1.66	Accepted
4.	Husbands		2.10	0.85				
5.	Homemakers	240	3.66	0.70	119	1.12	1.47	Accepted
6.	Husbands		3.13	0.78				

7.	Homemakers	240	3.18	0.81	119	1.82	1.98	Accepted
8.	Husbands		3.28	0.67				
9.	Homemakers	240	1.66	0.85	119	1.28	1.96	Accepted
10.	Husbands		2.46	0.79				
T-test Value			0.97	1.61	Accepted			

From t-test value (Table 4) shows that the hypothesis is accepted because the grand t-test value for t-calculated is 0.97, which is less than 1.96 grand t-test of t- critical at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis was upheld. Page | 358

The result of the findings revealed that homemakers income management strategies include: planned spending habit, spending money within the limit of family income, homemakers prefer buying items in the market, Family needs always arranged according to their priority, and homemakers depending mainly on homemade food. However, the grand mean score of 3.07 which is above the cut-point score of 2.50, therefore, indicates that these items were the income management strategies adopted by homemakers in Aba North LGA of Abia State. Furthermore, the result focused on homemakers' knowledge of financial management and this agreed with Wachukwu-Chikodi (2019) who stated that homemaker as a financial manager of the family must understand financial management tips in order to succeed. This is also in line with the finding of Otoritas, (2013); Northhouse (2007) who stated that efficient management and judicious use of resources or income is instituted to enable the family meet or accomplish its set objectives in education, health care, feeding, shelter, clothing. However, the study by Kotter (2001) opined that it is only 17% of homemakers that has good financial management skills. The result of the findings also revealed that all the respondents agreed that there is no significance different between homemakers and their husbands on income management strategies adopted by the homemakers in the post-pandemic era. And the grand mean score of 3.40 which indicated that income saving management strategies by homemakers include: Investing part of the family fund, enrolling on family/women meeting, saving some of the fund in a box, and Saving family fund in the bank. This finding shows that understanding money saving management strategies helps homemakers to carry out regular saving strategies such as contributins, banking, and box savings which inturns increse productivity of the family and savings even at a difficult time. This is in an agreement with the work of Nwankwo (2003) who observed that homemakers' financial skills determine the family's financial success.

Finally, the findings of the study also revealed homemakers as family's financial managers who have their source of incomes from: gift, selling of farm products, contributions, trading, salary/wages and stipends. The study went further to show that the income generated from family's financial management are spend on family's needs like: education, health care, feeding, clothing, and sheltering. However, homemakers adopted saving strategies of: buying in buck, buying in the market, budget, spending within family's financial incomes limit so as to safe the family from debt. The following limitations were observed. The possibility that some of the respondents may not be sincere with their responses may affect the result. Nevertheless, the number of the responses was adequate for making meaningful inferences. Also, the respondents coming from different works of life might have affected their responses. However, their response was similar to each other. Based on the findings, the following recommendations such as establishment of financial training center should be adopted by the by the government for the rural dwellers, management

training should be encourage at home, instead of enslaving house helps, members of the family apart from the wife should be part of management in the family and homemakers should be courageously prudent in dealing with available resources.

4. Conclusion

The findings of this study have revealed that there exist positive relationships between home makers and their husbands on income management strategies and saving management strategies adopted by the homemakers in post pandemic era in Abia State. Therefore, if the findings of this study are published and made known to Abia State agricultural development programs, it would serve as a guide in organizing training for homemakers for effective economics enhancement. Furthermore, if findings of the study are made known to the government, it would serve as a supervisory template. They will know the areas to supervise homemakers on and proffer guidance and assistance where necessary for improvement of home management strategies. The following were suggested for further study based on the findings of this study: determinants of effective management strategies for improving homemakers' income; skills acquisition training needs of homemakers for enhancing their saving management strategies; and relationship between husbands, wives (homemakers) and children' for effectiveness improvement of homemakers management strategies.

Page | 359

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest as they harmoniously executed the research process

Author Contributions

The research topic was designed, introduced and developed by Amarachi Igwe. Titus Akpan carried out the analysis of the samples and interpretation of the data. Both Amarachi Igwe and Titus Akpan collected the data. Both authors also participated in proofreading the article in turns approved the final draft for publication.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further requires can be directed to the corresponding author

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References

- Adam, C., Henstridge, M., & Lee, S. (2020). After the lockdown: macroeconomic adjustment to the COVID-19 pandemic in sub-Saharan Africa. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, *graa023*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/graa023>
- Despard, M., Grinstein-Weiss, M., Chun, Y., & Roll, S. (2020). COVID-19 Job and income Loss Leading to More Hunger and Financial Hardship: Booking Institution. Retrieved from <https://bookings.edu/up-front>(accessed October 22, 2022).
- Eboh, E. M., Akpata, G. O., & Akintoye, A. E. (2016). Health Care Financing in Nigeria: An Assessment of NHIS. *European Journal of Business & Management*, *8*, 27-43.
- Kotter, J. P. (2001) What leaders really do? *Harvard Business Review*, *19*, 85-96.
- Nguyen, P. H., Frongillo, E. A., Sanghi, T., Wable, G., Mahmud, Z., Tran, L. M., & Menon, P. (2018). Engagement of husbands in material nutrition program substantially contributed to greater intake of micro-nutrients supplement: Results of crusher-randomized program evaluation in Bangladesh. *The Journal of Nutrition*, *148*, 1352-1363. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/nxy090>
- Northhouse, P. (2007). *Leadership theory and practice*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Nwankwo, J. N. (2003). *Family Financial Management: A Practical Guide*. Ugeheili: Eddy-Joe Publishers, 130-136.
- Otoritas, J. K. (2013). Financial Literacy. Financial Service Authority. Retrieved from <http://bangradja.blogspot.co.id/2021/06/literasikeuangan-pada-tanggal-19.html>. (accessed October 22, 2022).
- Scheresberg, C. D. B. (2013). Financial Literacy and Financial Behaviour among Young Adult: Evidence and Implication. *Numeracy*, *6*, 25. <https://doi.org/10.5038/1936-4660.6.2.5>
- Sophie, H., Rhiannon, M., Tom, S. & Alice, W. (2020). Poverty in the Pandemic: the Impact of the Coronavirus on Low-income Families and Children. Retrieved from <https://cpaj.org.UK/sites/default/files/files/policypost/poverty-in-the-pandemic.pdf>. (accessed October 12, 2022).
- Wachukwu-Chikodi, Happiness I, Deedam, Nua J., & Wordu G. (2019). Income Management Practices of Homemakers Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Home Science*, *5*, 138-143

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